

Comparative Study in Type 1 Tympanoplasty–Umbrella Technique (Perichondrium with Cartilage Composite Graft) Vs Temporalis Fascia Graft in Tertiary Care Hospital

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Perforation of tympanic membrane in Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media is usually surgically corrected by Tympanoplasty. Various graft materials are tried for its reconstruction like periosteum, perichondrium, cartilage, vein & fat. The cartilage with perichondrium was used as a composite graft to study the long term results.

Aim of the Study: To evaluate and compare the results in terms of uptake, auditory gain and complications using umbrella technique (perichondrium with cartilage) composite graft versus temporalis fascia graft in the patients who underwent Type–1 tympanoplasty.

Materials: A prospective observational study was conducted on 60 CSOM patients with Tubotympanic type of disease. In 30 patients cartilage graft and in another 30 patients Temporalis fascia graft was used for Tympanoplasty Type-I. The graft uptake, Air conduction hearing threshold gain and complications were observed over a period of 06 months and the data was analysed.

Results: The graft uptake was 100% in the cartilage graft group and 93.3% in the Temporalis fascia group. Air conduction hearing gain was unequivocal in the two groups and the p value was <0.05.

Conclusions: The graft uptake in Umbrella technique (Perichondrium with cartilage composite graft) showed 100% success rate when compared with temporalis fascia graft. it was 93.3%. The hearing improvement in Umbrella technique (perichondrium with cartilage composite graft) was almost equal without any significant difference when compared with temporalis fascia graft technique group.

Keywords: CSOM, central perforation, Graft, Composite graft, Tympanoplasty and auditory gain.

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Introduction

Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media (CSOM) is a chronic inflammatory disease of middle ear cleft clinically characterized by ear discharge, diminished hearing and pathological changes in the Tympanic membrane in the form of permanent perforation and mastoid Osteitis. [1] CSOM is seen in all age groups and both the genders. [2] CSOM is preceded by Acute Suppurative Otitis Media always, when fails to resolve totally leads to the above clinical features. [3] The prevalence of CSOM in India is 11.25%. [4] CSOM is treated during its acute infective period with broad spectrum antibiotics. [5] The permanent pathological changes in the form of mucoperiosteitis of the middle ear cleft and permanent perforation of the tympanic membrane needs to be corrected by

surgery. [6] The crux of the surgical treatment consists of total eradication of the mucosal and osteitis of the middle ear cleft by mastoidectomy and followed by reconstruction of the hearing mechanism by performing Tympanoplasty with or without ossiculoplasty. [7] In the literature the term “Tympanoplasty” denotes an operation to eradicate disease in the middle ear cleft and to reconstruct the mechanism of hearing without mastoid surgery, with or without tympanic membrane grafting' as termed by the American academy of ophthalmology and otolaryngology committee. [8] The term Tympanoplasty with mastoidectomy is used when a mastoid procedure is included [10] is used. In 1953 the term Tympanoplasty was first used by Wull-

stein to describe operative techniques for reconstruction of the hearing mechanism in the middle ear that had been impaired or destroyed by chronic ear disease. [11] As reported by Shambaugh, in 1640, Benzer recommended pig's bladder membrane stretched over an ivory tube. Yearsley in the year 1841, applied as simple ball of moist cotton against the perforation; a method still used occasionally even today. Toynbee in 1853 devised a thin rubber disc with a silver wire stem to assist in its placement, artificial membrane tympani' and produced a hearing improvement. [12] The operating microscope was first used to these operations by Wullstein and Zollner in the year 1951, has become in dispensable for this type of surgery. [13] Heerman [14] was first used Temporalis fascia as a grafting material in the year 1958. In 1960 Shea and Tabb described the closure using a vein graft, by placing it medial to the tympanic membrane [15]. The success of this technique gave rise to new procedure known as underlay procedure and later on with the use of connective tissue, as most problems incurred with free skin grafts were eliminated. Temporalis fascia was popularized by Storrs in 1961. [16] Cartilage has been used successfully in middle ear procedures for first time by Sahan et al in 2014 [17]. It has been shown that cartilage is well tolerated with minimal resorption time and survives for a long period with good hearing results. Mauri M et al [18] compared results of inlay cartilage butterfly grafts and underlay temporalis fascia grafts. They investigated the graft take up rates & hearing outcomes at 1 month and 2 months respectively. They included only those perforations where the size of perforation was less than 50% of the size of the tympanic membrane. They did not detect any significant difference in either the graft take rates or hearing improvement. Mohamad et al [19] have concluded that tympanoplasty using cartilage with or without perichondrium has better morphological outcome than tympanoplasty using temporalis fascia. They noted that there was no statistically significant difference in hearing outcomes between the 2 grafts. Yung et al, [8] concluded that graft uptake rate for cartilage (80%) Versus fascia (84.2%) mean hearing gain for cartilage (12.60dB) versus fascia (13.63dB), post-operative air- bone gap of 20 dB cartilage (41.6%) versus fascia (64.4%) & there was No statistically significant difference in graft take or hearing. The present study was conducted to evaluate and compare the results in terms of uptake, auditory gain and complications using umbrella technique (perichondrium with cartilage) composite graft versus temporalis fascia graft in the patients who underwent Type-1 Tympanoplasty.

Materials

A prospective observational study was conducted on 60 CSOM patients with Tubotympanic type of

disease. In 30 patients cartilage graft and in another 30 patients Temporalis fascia graft was used for Tympanoplasty Type-I. The graft uptake, Air conduction hearing threshold gain and complications were observed over a period of 06 months and the data was analysed.

Source of Data: 60 patients diagnosed with CSOM Tubo-tympanic type with dry central perforation were subjected to Type-1 Tympanoplasty in the Department of ENT, Government Medical College, Anantapuamu, A.P. were included.

Period of Study: June 2023 to May 2024.

Type of Study: A comparative, prospective and analytical study.

60 patients attending with complaints diminished hearing and previously having history of discharge from the ear were included. An ethics committee of the Institute approved the study and proforma and consent forms approved by the committee were used.

Inclusion criteria: Patients with CSOM with total or Sub-total central perforation with Dry ear for at least 6 weeks were included. Patients aged between 18 and 55 years were included. Patient with pure conductive type of hearing loss were included. Patients with permanent perforation were included.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with Sensory neural hearingloss were excluded. Patients aged below 18 years and above 50 years were excluded. Patients with poor general condition were excluded. Patients with Attico-antral type of CSOM were excluded. Patients clinically proved to have developed Cholesteatoma; Aural Polypi & granulations were excluded. Patients with Ossicular chain discontinuity and Atelectatic tympanic membranes were excluded.

Method of collection of data: A total of 60 patients who were satisfying the above criteria is taken for the study through a systematic approach of clinical symptoms, tuning fork tests, endoscopic examination, general examination, ENT examination, microscopic examination, pure tone audiometry and routine blood investigations and X-ray both mastoids. The total 60 patients were randomly assigned into two groups with 30 each based on the type of approach followed. Then Tympanoplasty surgery was performed with consent of patients under local anesthesia through post aural approach.

Group-A: 30 patients underwent Type-1 Tympanoplasty Umbrella technique. (Perichondrium with cartilage) composite graft and Group- B: Another 30 patients were subjected to Type-1 Tympanoplasty by using temporalis fascia as the graft material. Then post-operative graft uptake, hearing improvement was re-assessed. Then follow up was done for a period of 6 months. Hearing threshold

evaluated post-operatively after 06 months at three frequencies; 0.5, 1, 2KHZ and a pure tone average were calculated. All the patients had undergone pre-anesthetic checkup and patients consent was taken for Tympanoplasty after explaining advantages and disadvantages of each approach and complications of surgery. Local anesthesia was preferred as the intubation related complications, bleeding and operation time can be reduced. Karl ZEISS microscope was used for surgery. The television monitor was placed on the other side of the table, across the patient's head. Routine microscopic ear surgery instruments were used.

Surgical Technique: In all the Patients surgery was done through post aurial approach.

Premedication: The patients were premedicated half an hour prior to the procedure with 30mg Pentazocine and 25 mg Phenergan, given intramuscularly. All procedures were performed under Local Anaesthesia.

Position of the patient: The patient was placed in

the supine position with the head partially rotated to the opposite side.

Infiltration: The post auricular infiltration given with 2% Xylocaine with 1: 1, 00, 000 adrenaline. The canal wall infiltration was done by using a 2ml syringe with 26-gauge needle with the terminal 1 cm angulated towards the bevel. Post-aural William-wilde's incision was used.

Harvesting the Graft: In Group-A tragal cartilage was harvested with intact perichondrium on one side.

Carving of cartilage: Cartilage is sculptured into Tri-limbed cartilage spokes & adjusting the length of the limbs. A 'X' shaped cut at the junction of three limbs to make three individual cartilage segments.

Removal of a triangular shaped bit of cartilage to accommodate the handle of Malleus was done. The side of the cartilage graft without perichondrium was kept towards the middle ear space. (Fig 1, 2 and 3)

Figure1: Showing the tragal cartilage harvested and sculptured into tri-limbed cartilage spokes

Figure 2: Showing the X-cut at the junction of three limbs

Summary of Steps of Carving the Cartilage:**Figure 3: Showing a brief view of steps of carving the cartilage**

In group B patients- Temporal is fascia graft was harvested through the same post auricular incision. (Fig 4)

Figure 4: Showing the harvesting the temporalis fascia graft

Position of the surgical microscope: The surgical microscope is positioned at the head of the table. The Tympanic membrane with its perforation was visualized.

Freshening of the perforation margins: Freshening of the perforation margins was done using a wide curved pick.

Incision and flap elevation: An incision was given from 1 O'clock to 5 o'clock in right ear and 11 O'clock to 7 o'clock in left ear in the canal wall skin about 5mm away from the annulus and the Tympan meatal flap was elevated by using round knife.

Middle ear inspection: The middle ear findings were noted with reference to Malleus, Incus and the

Stapes and mobility of Incudo-stapedial joints. The Eustachian tube opening, the oval and the round window were also visualized; the round window reflex was visualized to confirm the continuity of the ossicular chain.

Graft placement: Graft placed by under lay technique in all the patients in the present study.

Repositioning of the tympan meatal flap: The Tympan meatal flap was replaced on the graft in its original position. Gel foam pieces soaked in antibiotic ear drops over the skin flap to make the skin in approximation to graft. Only a small ointment pack was kept covering the external auditory canal. Hemostasis secured; suturing done in layers. Mastoid bandage applied. (Fig 5)

Figure 5: Showing the endoscopic image after placing the umbrellacartilaginous composite graft

Post-operative treatment–follow-up: For Group A: Inj. Ceftriaxone-1gm IV twice daily for 07 days, Oral antibiotics from 3rd day to 8th day; Decongestant Tablets given for 2 weeks. Analgesic and anti-inflammatory tablets were given for 2 weeks. Ear pack was removed on 7th post op day Sutures were removed on 7th postop day.

For Group B: Inj. Ceftriaxone-1gm IV twice daily for 05 days. Decongestant Tablets given for 2 weeks. Analgesic and anti-inflammatory tablets, Oral antibiotics from 5th to 10th day were given. Mastoid bandage and sutures were removed on 7th

postoperative day. Patients are followed up for an average period of 06 months to assess Graft uptake. Hearing assessment and presence of Complications were assessed at each visit. And the post-operative graft uptake, the hearing improvement was assessed after six months by comparing preoperative air conduction thresholds and postoperative air conduction thresholds. The hearing threshold was evaluated at three frequency average of 0.5, 1, and 2 kHz. Fig 6 and 7 show the pre and post-operative otoscopy picture of the Tympanic membrane.

Figure 6: Showing the pre–op tympanic membrane with central perforation

Figure7: Showing the post-op image of tympanic membrane

Statistic Analysis: Data were entered in MS-Excel and analyzed in SPSS V21. Descriptive statistics were represented with percentages, Mean with SD. Chi-square test, Independent t-test, Paired t-test were calculated to find significance. P<0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Observation & Results: The present study was conducted during the period June 2023 to May 2024 wherein 60 patients were selected who attending ENT OPD, Government Medical College, Anantapuramu, with dry central perforation of Tubo-tympanic type of CSOM, the results and analysis are as follows. The study group included 60 patients which are divided into two groups 30 each, based on the type of approach followed.

Demographic data:

Among the 60 patients with CSOM included, there were 38 (63.3%) females and 22 (36.75%) with a male to female ratio of 1:1.72. Among the 60 patients 30 patients were treated with Umbrella type of cartilage fascia graft (Group A) and 30 patients were treated with temporalis fascia alone (Group

B). Among the 38 female patients 20 (52.63%) underwent Tympanoplasty with umbrella type cartilage and fascia graft and 18 (47.36%) patients underwent Tympanoplasty with temporalis fascia alone.

Among the 22/60 male patients 10 (33.33%) patients underwent Tympanoplasty with umbrella type cartilage and 12 (40%) patients with Temporalis fascia graft alone. (Table 1)

Patients aged from 18 to 25 were 24 (40%) and out of these patients 13 (43.3%) belonged to Group- A and 11 (36.7%) patients belonged to Group-B. Patients aged from 26 to 35 were 16 (23.3%) and out of these patients 07 (23.3%) belonged to Group- A and 09 (30%) patients belonged to Group-B.

Patients aged from 36 to 45 were 16 (26.7%) and out of these patients 08 (26.7%) belonged to Group- A and 08 (26.7%) patients belonged to Group-B. Patients aged from 46 to 55 were 04 (06.7%) and out of these patients 02 (06.7%) belonged to Group- A and 02 (06.7%) patients belonged to Group-B. (Table 1)

Table 1: Showing the Demographic data of the patients (n-60; Group-A: 30; Group-B: 30)

Observation	Umbrella Group(U)	Temporalis Fascia Group (T)
SEX		
FEMALE- 38	20(66.7%)	18(60%)
MALE- 22	10(33.3%)	12 (40%)
AGE in Years		
18 to 25- 24 (40%)	13 (43.3%)	11 (36.7%)
26 to 35- 16 (26.7%)	07 (23.3%)	09 (30.0%)
36 to 45- 16 (26.7%)	08 (26.7%)	08 (26.7%)
46 to 55- 04 (06.7%)	02 (06.7%)	02 (06.7%)

Symptomatology: The predominant symptom of the CSOM in the study group was ear discharge in 46 patients

(76.7%) and hard of hearing in 38 patients (63.3%) and the less common symptoms were ear pain in 35 (58.3%) and tinnitus in 22 patients (36.7%). (Table 2)

Table 2: Symptomatology in the study groups

Symptoms	Temporalis fascia group		Umbrella group		Total	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Ear Discharge	23	76.7%	23	76.7%	46	76.7%
Hard of Hearing	17	56.7%	21	70.0%	38	63.3%
Pain in the Ear	19	63.3%	16	53.3%	35	58.3%
Tinnitus	8	26.7%	14	46.7%	22	36.7%

Among the 60 patients with CSOM the right ear was involved in 22 (36.7%) patients and in 24 (40%) patients the left ear.

Bilateral symptoms were least commonly noted in only 14 (23.3%) patients. Among the 22 patients with CSOM in the right ear 09 (30%) belonged to the Group A and 13 (43.35) belonged to the Group

B. Similarly among the 24 patients with CSOM in the left ear 12 (40%) were allotted to Group, and the remaining 12 (40%) were allotted to the Group B. (Table 3).

Among the 14 patients with bilateral CSOM, 09 (30%) were allotted to Group A, and the remaining 05 were allotted to the Group B (Table 3).

Table 3: Showing the side of involvement with CSOM in the subjects. (n- 60; Group-A: 30; Group-B: 30)

Laterality	Number	Percentage (%)
Right- 22 (36.7%)		
Group-A	09	30
Group-B	13	43.3
Left - 24 (40%)		
Group-A	12	40
Group-B	12	40
Bilateral 14 (23.3%)		
Group-A	09	30
Group-B	05	16.7

In group A, 18 (60%) patients had subtotal perforation, and 12 (63.3%) patients had Total perforation. In Group B, 12 (40%) patients had total perforation, and 11 (36.7%) patients had Total perforation.

In total there were 37 (61.7%) patients with subtotal perforations and 23 (38.3%) patients with total perforations. (Table 4) Air conduction thresholds of patients in the Group A, were between 20 and 30 in 05 (08.33%), between 30 and 40 in 11 (36.7%), between 40 and 50 in 13 (21.67%), and between 50

and 60 in 02 (03.33%) patients. In group B, Air conduction thresholds were between 20 and 30 in 04 (03.33%), between 30 and 40 in 10 (16.67%), between 40 and 50 in 13 (21.67%), and between 50 and 60 in 02 (03.33%) patients. (Table 4)

There was no statistical significant difference between the two groups in terms of selection of patients with Air conduction thresholds. p value was 0.53, which was more than 0.05 (p taken as significant at <0.05).

Table 4: Showing the type of perforation in each group and the Air conduction threshold values in the study (n- 60; Group-A: 30; Group-B: 30)

Observation	Group A	Group B	P value
Type of Perforation			
Sub- total central perforation- 37 (61.7%)	18- (60%)	19- (63.3%)	0.53
Total Perforation- 23 (38.3%)	12- (40%)	11- (18.33%)	0.51
Air conduction Thresholds			
20 to 30 dB- 09 (15%)	05- (08.33%)	04- (03.33%)	0.024
30 to 40 dB- 21 (35%)	11- (18.33%)	10- (16.67%)	
40 to 50 dB- 26 (43.3%)	13- (21.67%)	13- (21.67%)	
50 to 60 dB- 04 (06.7%)	02- (03.33%)	02- (03.33%)	

Post- operative air conduction thresholds after 06 months: Majority of the patients of the study group has air conduction thresholds between 10 to 40decibels, 07 patients had air conduction thresh-

olds within 40 to 50 decibels. One patient had air conduction thresholds between 50-60 decibels. In group A- In Umbrella group-11 patients had post-operative air conduction thresholds between 20-30

decibels, 08 patients had postoperative air conduction thresholds between 10-20 decibels, 07 patients had in the range between 30-40 decibels, post-operative air conduction thresholds of 04 patients was between 40 – 50 decibels range. In Group B-Temporalis fascia group -11 patients had post-operative air conduction thresholds between 20-30 decibels, 10 patients had post-operative hearing between 30-40 decibels, 05 patients had between 10-20 decibels, 03 patients between 40-50 decibels and 01 patient had 50-60 decibels. Calculated p value was 0.67 which is more than 0.05, hence there was no significant difference in post-operative air conduction thresholds between the two groups. (Table 5) About 23 patients in the study group has hearing improvement between 10-15 decibels, 20 patients had hearing improvement within 5-10 decibels, 08 patients had hearing improvement within 05 decibels, while 07 patients were in the range of 15-20 decibels, very few had hearing improvement measuring more than 20 decibels. In Umbrella technique study group-majority of the patients had hearing improvement between 10-15decibels, 10 patients between 5-10 decibels,

05 patients between 15-20 decibels, 03 patients within 5 decibels. In Temporalis fascia study group - majority of the patients had hearing improvement between 10-15 decibels, 10 patients had hearing improvement between 05-10 decibels, 05 patients within 05 decibels, only 04 patients had hearing improvement between 15-25 decibels. Calculated p value was 0.43 which was more than 0.05, hence there was no significant difference in post-operative hearing improvement between the two groups. (Table 5) In Umbrella group –out of total 30 patients included in the study group, graft uptake was good in all the patients. In Temporalis fascia group, out of total 30 patients included in the study group, graft uptake was good in about 28 patients. In Umbrella study group –out of total 30patients, graft was intact in all the 30 patients and no complications were noted. In Temporalis fascia study group, out of total 30patients, graft was intact in 28 (93.3%) patients. In both the groups the uptake rate was good and the gain in the Air conduction was also good with a p value of 0.001 which was significant. (Table 5)

Table5:Post-operative follow up after 06 months in terms of results like graft uptake, Hearing gain in the two groups. (n- 60; Group-A: 30; Group-B: 30)

Observation	Group A	Group B	P value
Post-operative graft uptake			
Total uptake	30 (100%)	28 (93.3%)	0.001
Residual perforation	0 (0%)	02 (06.7%)	
Post-operative Air conduction thresholds			
10 to 20 dB- 13 (21.7%)	08 (26.7%)	05 (16.7%)	0.054
20 to 30 dB- 22 (36.7%)	11 (36.7%)	11 (36.7%)	
30 to 40 dB- 17 (28.3%)	07 (23.3%)	10 (33.3%)	
40 to 50 dB- 07 (11.7%)	04 (13.33%)	03 (10.0%)	
50 to 60 dB- 01 (01.7%)	0 (0%)	01 (03.3%)	
Improvement if in Air conduction thresholds			
0- 5 dB -08 (16.7%)	3 (10.0%)	05 (16.7%)	0.067
5 to 10 dB- 20 (33.3%)	10 (33.3%)	10 (33.3%)	
10 to 15 dB- 23 (38.3%)	12 (40%)	11 (36.7%)	
15 to 20 dB- 07 (11.7%)	05 (16.7%)	02 (06.7%)	
20 to 25 dB- 02 (06.7%)	0 (0%)	02 (06.7%)	
Post-operative complications			
Total uptake	30 (100%)	28 (93.3%)	
Residual perforation	0 (0%)	02 (06.7%)	

Discussion:

CSOM is one of the common Otological Problem in the developing world. It leads to varying degree of conductive hearing loss and also sensorineural hearing loss. The operating microscope was first applied to the microscopic ear surgeries by Wullstein and Zollner [3] in the year 1951.

Temporalis fascia remains the most frequently used graft material, with tympanic membrane closure rates of 80–90 percent for primary tympanoplasty surgeries in different hands. [13] The use of cartilage in middle-ear reconstruction is not a new con-

cept. Advantages of the cartilage graft include its very low metabolic rate and ability to receive nutrients by diffusion. It is also very easy to work with because it is pliable, resists deformation from pressure variations and incorporates well into the tympanic membrane. [16] Failure in tympanoplasty may be due to a variety of reasons, such as properties of the graft used, operation technique, or patient-related reasons. [18] It is reported that factors like ear atelectasis, Eustachian tube dysfunction, Tympanosclerosis, active suppuration, condition of middle ear mucosa, wide perforation, and revision myringoplasty, are the reasons for low success rates

in the use of temporal fascia. [11] This study aimed to compare the results in Type-I Tympanoplasty by using temporalis Fascia graft versus tragal cartilage with perichondrium (umbrella technique) as the graft materials in a total of 60 patients with tubo tympanic type of CSOM during the period of 18 months i.e, January 2018 to August 2019. The present study includes total 60 patients, of which 38 (63.3%) females and 22 (36.75%) males with a ratio of F: M ratio of 1.72: 1. It was a female predominant group, which is in accordance with the study conducted by Sood AS, et al [20] et al., they reported the female: male ratio – 1.85: 1. And in a study conducted by Xabier Altuna [21] et al., reported that the female: male ratio – 2.09: 1. All the above studies showed commonly female preponderance. The present study includes the patients belonging to age group of 18 to 50 years with a mean age of presentation is 30 years. The maximum numbers of patients were belonging to 18 to 25 years age range i.e, around 40%. The age distribution of the study is comparable to study done by Sood AS et al [20]. In Comparative study of type I tympanoplasty using temporalis fascia and tragal cartilage with perichondrium as graft material, in this study the mean age of presentation was 34.4 years with a range 15-60 years. In a study conducted by Maurietal [18], the age distribution was 15 – 65 years, whereas in a study done by Al lackany & Sarkis [22] the age range is 10 – 60 years, while in a study conducted by Xabier Altuna [21] et al., the age distribution was 13–73 years. In the present study of the 60 patients ear discharge was the predominant symptom, observed in 46 patients followed by hard of hearing, ear pain and finally the ringing sensation of ear. In the present study group of 60 patients the symptoms localized to right ear in 22 (36%) patients and left ear in 24 (40%) patients and the bilateral symptoms were least common noted in only 14 (23%) patients. In a study done by Sood AS et al [20], Twenty-seven (67.5%) patients had unilateral disease and 13 (32.5%) had bilateral chronic otitis media. Whereas in study done by Gurshinderpal Singh Shergil [23] et al., Out of a total of 120 cases, majority had left side CSOM 39% 47 cases, followed by bilateral tube tympanic type 39 cases 32.5% and right side 28.3% 34 cases of CSOM. Aidonis I, Robertson TC, Sismanis A (2005) [24] in their study of 48 patients, recorded a bilateral tympanic membrane perforation in 25% of patients. John B Booth (1974,) [25] in his study of 284 cases, found the incidence of bilateral discharge to be 30%. In the present study group of 60 patients, 37 patients (61.7%) were having Subtotal CP and 23 patients (38.3%) were having Total CP. In a study conducted in 120 patients by Gurshinderpal Singh Shergill, Dipak Ranjan Nayak [23], et al., 71 patients had a large perforation (> 50% area of pars tensa), 36 medium perforations (25 - 50% area of pars tensa),

9 subtotal perforation (only annulus present) and 4 patients had small perforation (< 25% area of pars tensa). Munish Kambatattii Shekharappa [26] et al. conducted a study - Cartilage Myringoplasty and observed an Ideal Grafting Technique for Complex Perforations, Out of 30 cases who underwent Type-1 tympanoplasty, 24 patients (80%) had large central and subtotal perforations five patients had medium central perforation with remnant tympanic membrane showing sclerotic plaque and atrophic changes. Only one patient had a total perforation. The post-operative graft uptake rate in various studies was depicted in the table below. In a study conducted by MCavaliere [27] et al., showed 99.35% graft success rate and in this study cartilage with perichondrium was used as the graft material. And a study conducted by Dornhoffer J [9] reported graft success rate of 97.6%, by using perichondrium with Cartilage Island as the graft material. In another study conducted by Aidonis I [28] et al concluded that graft success rate is 98.4% and the cartilage shield was used as a graft material, and in a study conducted by Vadiya S [29] et al., 98.46% is the graft uptake rate and the cartilage with perichondrium was used as the graft material, In a study conducted by Garcia RB [30] et al., reported that 71.1% is the graft uptake rate and cartilage was used as the graft material, and in another study conducted by Chen XW, Yang H et al [31] et al., the graft uptake rate is 96.1% and the cartilage with perichondrium was used as the graft material. The results of present study in Group A showed 100% graft uptake rate by using cartilage with perichondrium as the graft material and the present study which was conducted in a 60 patients only with advanced microscopes with recent trained skills was almost comparable with the results of the studies conducted by recent ENT surgeons of different countries. As mentioned in the above table graft uptake rate by various authors were 86.67% graft uptake in a study conducted by Dornhoffer & Singh [9] et al., 88.8% in a study done by Rizerand in a study conducted by Dabholkar [32] et al., 84 % was the graft uptake rate and 90 % in a study done by Sood AS [20] et al. Whereas it is reported 75% in a study done by Zulkifal Awan [33] et al., and 86.1% reported in a study conducted by Kalcioğlu [34] et al., and the results of present study i.e; 93.3% graft uptake rate is as comparable with the similar studies as mentioned earlier. In the present study group i.e., in Group – A, the minimum pre-operative air conduction threshold is 25.0 db and the maximum pre-operative air conduction threshold is 55.0 db and the mean pre-operative air conduction threshold is 39.20 db with a standard deviation of 8.18. The minimum post-operative air conduction threshold is 17.0 db and the maximum post-operative air conduction threshold is 46.0 db and the mean post-operative air conduction threshold is 28.53 db with a standard deviation of 8.90

and the p value is < 0.001 which is less than 0.05 hence there is statistically significant difference in the pre-operative and post-operative air conduction thresholds. In the present study group i.e., in Group – B, the minimum pre-operative air conduction threshold is 26.0 db and the maximum pre-operative air conduction threshold is 55.0 db and the mean pre-operative air conduction threshold is 40.87db with a standard deviation of 8.02. The minimum post-operative air conduction threshold is 15.0 db and the maximum post-operative air conduction threshold is 51.0 db and the mean post-operative air conduction threshold is 30.57db with a standard deviation of 10.03 and the p value was <0.001 which is less than 0.05 hence there is statistically significant difference in the pre-operative and post-operative air conduction thresholds. In a Tertiary Care Centre reported that pre-operative air conduction threshold was 45.62 db and post-operative air conduction threshold was 34.17 dB and the calculated P value is <0.001 which is less than $P < 0.05$ hence, there is a significant difference in between the two groups. In the present study the hearing improvement was defined by comparing the pre-op air conduction and post op air conduction threshold calculated p value for hearing improvement between two groups is 0.43 which was more than 0.05; hence there was no significant difference in hearing outcome between the two groups. In Umbrella study group - out of total 30 patients, graft was intact in all the 30 patients and no complications were noted. In Temporalis fascia study a group - out of total 30 patients, graft was intact in 28 patients, whereas residual CP was noted in 2 patients of the study group. In a study conducted by Murat Şahan [35] et al., Out of total 33 cases 3 patients had a residual CP in temporalis fascia study group. Sood AS (20) et al., conducted a Comparative study of type I tympanoplasty using temporalis fascia and tragal cartilage with perichondrium as graft material reported that out of total 40 patients each group with 20 patients underwent tympanoplasty, 2 patients had residual CP in temporalis fascia group and only one patient had residual CP in cartilage group.

Conclusions:

The graft uptake in Umbrella technique (perichondrium with cartilage composite graft) showed 100% success rate when compared with temporalis fascia graft it is 93.3%. The hearing improvement in Umbrella technique (perichondrium with cartilage composite graft) was almost equal without any significant difference when compared with temporalis fascia graft technique group.

References

1. De Seta E, Covelli E, De Seta D, Mancini Filippo R: Cartilage how to reduce surgery time.

- J Laryngol Otol 2010;124: 784–785.
2. Zhang ZG, Huang QH, Zheng YQ, Sun W, Chen YB, Si Y. Three autologous substitutes for myringoplasty: a comparative study. *Otol Neurotol.* 2011; 32:1234–38
3. Zo'llner F. The principles of plastic surgery of the sound conducting apparatus. *J Laryngol Otol.* 1995; 69:65-69.
4. Wulstein HL. Funktionelle Operationen im Mittelohrmithilfe desfreien Spaltlappentransplantates. *Arch Otorhinolaryngol* 1952; 16: 422Y435
5. Domhoffer JL. (1997): Hearing results with cartilage tympanoplasty. *Laryngoscope*; 107: 1094-9.
6. Kazikdas KC, Onal K, Boyraz I, Karabulut E. (2007): Palisade cartilage tympanoplasty for management of subtotal perforations: a comparison with the temporalis fascia technique. *Eur Arch Otorhinolaryngol*; 264:985-989.
7. TosM. Cartilage tympanoplasty methods: proposal of a classification. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 2008; 139:747–58
8. Yung M. Cartilage tympanoplasty: literature review. *J LaryngolOtol*2008; 122:663–72
9. Dornhoffer JL. Cartilage tympanoplasty: indications, techniques, and outcomes in a 1000 patient series. *Laryngoscope.* 2003; 113:1844-56.
10. Boone RT, Gardner EK, Dornhoffer JL. Success of cartilage grafting in revision tympanoplasty without mastoidectomy. *Otol Neurotol.* 2004; 25:678-81.
11. Khan MM, ParabSR. Primary cartilage tympanoplasty: our technique and results. *Am J Otolaryngol* 2011; 32:381–7.
12. Albirmawy OA. Comparison between cartilage-perichondrium composite _ring'graft and temporalis fascia in type one tympanoplasty in children. *J LaryngolOtol*2010; 124:967–74
13. Committee on conservation of hearing of the American Academy of Ophthalmology and Otolaryngology. Standard classification for surgery of chronic ear disease. *ArchOtolaryngol.* 1965; 81:204-205.
14. Heermann J. Experiences with free transplantation of facia connective tissue of the temporalis muscle in tympanoplasty and reduction of the size of the radical cavity. Cartilage Bridge from the stapes to the lower border of the tympanic membrane. *Z LaryngolRhinol Otol* 1962; 41:141Y155.
15. Sismanis A. Tympanoplasty. Glasscock – Shambaugh surgery of the ear. Ed: 5, BC Decker Inc; 2003:463-83.
16. Berthold E. Ueber Myringoplastik. *Wein Med B11878*; 1: 1627-630.
17. Sahan M, Derin S, Deveer M, Saglam O, Cullu N, Sahan L. Factors Affecting Success and Results of Cartilage- Perichondrium Island Graft

- in Revision Tympanoplasty. *IntAdv Otol.* 2014;10(1):64-67.doi:10.5152/iao.2014.014.
18. Mauri M, Neto JFL, Fuchs SC.(2001) Evaluation of inlay butterfly cartilage tympanoplasty: a randomised clinical trial. *Laryngoscope* 111:1479Y8.
 19. S.H. Mohamad, I. Khan, and S.S.M. Hussain, —Is cartilage tympanoplasty more effective than fascia tympanoplasty? A systematic review, *Otology and Neurotology*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 699–705,2012.
 20. Sood AS et al. *International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery*, *Int J Otorhinolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2018 May;4(3):789-793.
 21. Altuna, Xabier & Navarro, Juan & Martinez, Zuriñe & Lobato, Rocío & Algaba, Jesús. Island cartilage myringoplasty. Anatomical and functional results in 122 cases. *Acta otorinolaringológica española.* 2009; 61: 100-5. 10.1016/S2173- 5735(10)70017-X.
 22. Al lackany M, Sarkis NN. Functional results after myringoplasty and Type 1 tympanoplasty with the use of different graft materials. *J Med Res Inst.* 2005; 26:369Y74.
 23. Gurshinderpal SinghShergillet.al., Cartilage Myringoplasty and observed an Ideal
 24. Grafting Technique for Complex Perforations ojolhns. 2016; 10.2:74- 79.
 25. Aidonis I, Robertson TC, Sismanis A. Cartilage shield tympanoplasty: A reliable technique. *Otol Neurotol.* 2005;26(5):838–41.
 26. Booth JB. Myringoplasty factors affecting results. Final report: *Journal of Laryngology and Otolgy* 1973 Nov; 87:1039-84.
 27. Shekharappa, Munish Kambatatti, and Shruthi Malavalli Siddappa. —Cartilage Myringoplasty: An Ideal Grafting Technique for Complex Perforations. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR;* 2017.11,7: 06-08.
 28. Cavaliere M, Mottola G, Rondinelli M, Iemma M. Tragal cartilage in tympanoplasty: Anatomic and functional results in 306 cases. *Acta Otorhinolaryngologica Italica.* 2009; 29:27–32.
 29. Aidonis I, Robertson TC, Sismanis A. Cartilage shield tympanoplasty: A reliable technique. *Otol Neurotol.* 2005; 26(5):838–41.
 30. Vadiya S, Parikh V, Shah S, Pandya P, Kansara A. Comparison of modified cartilage shield tympanoplasty with tympanoplasty using temporalis fascia only: Retrospective analysis of 142 cases. *Hindawi Publishing Corporation Scientifica.* 2016; 2016:8092328.
 31. Garcia RB, Suarez M- Varela, Conejeros T, Porras GA, Puchades VM, Galofre JD. Myringoplasties. A retrospective analysis of our surgical outcomes. *Acta Otorrinolaringol Esp.* 2011; 62(3):213–19.
 32. Chen XW, Yang H, Gao RZ, Yu R, Gao ZQ. Perichondrium/cartilage composite graft for repairing large tympanic membrane perforations and hearing improvement. *Chinese Medical Journal.* 2010;123(3):301–04.
 33. Dabholkar JP, Vora K, Sikdar A. Comparative study of underlay tympanoplasty with temporalis fascia and tragal perichondrium. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2007; 59:116-9.
 34. Zulkifal Awan, Habib Bashir, Altaf Hussain. Myringoplasty. A comparative study of different graft materials and various surgical techniques. *Ann Pak Inst Med Sci.* 2008;4(4):209-11.
 35. Kalcioğlu MT, Firat Y, Selimoğlu E. Cartilage tympanoplasty with island technique: A comparison with the temporalis muscle fascia technique. *Int Adv Otol.* 2009;5(1):45-50.
 36. Sahan M, Derin S, Deveer M, Sağlam O, Cullu N, Sahan L. Factors Affecting Success and Results of Cartilage- Perichondrium Island Graft in Revision Tympanoplasty. *Int Adv Otol.* 2014;10(1):64-67.doi:10.5152/iao.2014.014.